

ISic0812

I.Sicily inscription 0812

Language

Latin and Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di
Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108327

1. Eumeni vivas
2. Ἀλπείνιον Μάγνον
3. τὸν λαμπρότατον ὑπατ(ικὸν)
4. καὶ ἀγνότατον δικαστήν
5. βουλή καὶ δῆμος
6. Λιλυβαειτῶν διὰ τὰς
7. περὶ τὴν πατρίδα
8. εὐεργεσίας τὸν
9. πάτρωνα ἠμίψατο ἠμείψατο

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175808

EDR 108327

EDCS 10701750

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1966.0167

Barbieri, G. 1963. Due cippi di Marsala del IV sec. d.C.. *Kokalos*. 9: 225-252. At 232-242 no.2 tav. LXVIII

Calderone, S. 1959. Lilybaeum. In De Ruggerio, E.(eds.), *Dizionario Epigrafico di Antichità romane*. Rome. pp. 1069-1072. At 1072

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